

STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF CISPLATIN AND ETOPOSIDE

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ABSTRACT: Etoposide and cisplatin are antineoplastic drugs used in parental dosage forms in many kinds of cancer separately or in combination therapy. The objective of the work was to develop a simple and rapid RP-HPLC method for concurrent determination of etoposide and cisplatin, aiming its application in quality control analysis. A simultaneous determination method saves cost and time as both drugs can be injected into a single HPLC system without the need to change or re-equilibrate with a new mobile phase. The HPLC method was developed using X-Bridge phenyl, 150x4.6mm, 3.5 μ as stationary phase coupled with 40 volumes Acetonitrile and 60 volumes 0.1% TFA at 1.0 ml/min flow rate with PDA detection. In the proposed method, during simultaneous analysis cisplatin showed retention time of 2.461 min and etoposide 3.893 min within a continuous run of 6 min. The method was validated as per ICH Q2 R1 guidelines and all the parameters were found to be in good agreement with acceptance criteria. The method was found to be linear in the range 12.5-75 μ g/ml and 25-150 μ g/ml respectively for ETS & CSP respectively with R^2 more than 0.999. The regression equation for ETS was $y = 11699x + 3136.4$, $y = 16409x + 7883$ for CSP. The accuracy of the developed method was 100.3% and 99.97% for ETS & CSP which was within the limits of guidelines. Stability studies were performed as per ICH Q1 guidelines and the method was found to be stability indicating with peak purity in all types of degradation conditions. The proposed method can be used for the quality control of both medicaments simultaneously.

Keywords: Cisplatin, Etoposide, RP-HPLC, Stability studies, validation.

Etoposide and cisplatin are chemotherapy Medicaments used in parental dosage forms in many kinds of cancer separately or in combination therapy. They are used for the treatment of lung cancer by simultaneous administration. Etoposide [C₂₉H₃₂O₁₃] chemically known as (5*S*,5*aR*,8*aR*,9*R*)-5-[[[(2*R*,4*aR*,6*R*,7*R*,8*R*, 8*aS*) -7,8-dihydroxy- 2-methyl- 4,4*a*,6,7,8,8*a*-hexahydro pyrano[3,2-*d*] [1,3]dioxin-6-yl]oxy]-9-(4-hydroxy -3,5- dimethoxyphenyl) -5*a*,6,8*a*,9-tetrahydro -5*H*-[2] benzofuro [6,5-*f*][1,3] benzodioxol -8-one, is a Topoisomerase inhibitor, solid in state and is very soluble in methanol, chloroform; slightly soluble in ethanol, Sparingly soluble in water. Cisplatin [PtCl₂(NH₃)₂] chemically known as azane; dichloroplatinum is an Antineoplastic, immunomodulating agents and Cross-Linking Reagent, solid in state and is soluble in water, DMSO, PVP, DMF. Scheme 1 shows the chemical structure of Etoposide (ETS) and cisplatin (CSP). [1-4]

Scheme 1: chemical structure of Etoposide and Cisplatin

Anti-cancer drugs are highly toxic and have a narrow margin of safety. Even though Etoposide and cisplatin are not used in combination therapeutically, a simultaneous detection method allows plasma samples of both drugs to be injected into a single system without a change in the mobile phase. Besides saving time, the ability to simultaneously investigate two different but potentially hazardous agents may reduce exposures to the chemicals for the researchers. A simultaneous detection method may help to provide clinicians with fast plasma concentrations of both drugs and facilitate their therapeutic managements [5].

According to literature, there are different reported methods for both drugs individually and in combination with other drugs. There are only two reported HPLC methods for the simultaneous assay of Etoposide and cisplatin. [6-9]. Stability studies are not included in the reported methods. The present study focuses on the development and validation of a stability indicating RP HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Etoposide and cisplatin. Validation of the developed method was performed following ICH Q2 (R1) [10, 11] guidelines. Stability studies were performed following ICH Q1A (R2) and Q1B [12, 13] guidelines.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals: Acetonitrile, Ortho Phosphoric acid, Trifluoro acetic acid were procured from Rankem chemicals, India. HPLC grade Water (Milli Q, in-house production) was used in the study. Pure drugs ETS, CSP were obtained as gift samples from Shree Icon labs Vijayawada, A.P., India. All chemicals used are of HPLC grade & were obtained from Rankem Chemicals, Haryana, India.

Instruments: Waters Alliance HPLC equipped with 2695 pump, 2998 PDA- detector, Autoinjector, empower 2 software was utilized in the study. Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer, Ohaus Electronic balance, Eutech pH Meter, Phoenix 4.5 L digital ultrasonic cleaner, Bionics Scientific hot air oven, LG refrigerator and Millipore BM2EA9672R were used in the study.

Solution preparations:

Diluent: Acetonitrile was used as diluent.

Buffer: 1ml OPA was dissolved in 1lt water. pH of the solution was observed to be 2.2

Mobile phase: ACN & buffer solution were mixed in the ratio of 20:80 and filtered through 0.45 μ membrane filter paper.

Standard solution: 100 mg Cisplatin and 50 mg Etoposide were weighed separately into 100 ml standard flasks and volume was made up to mark with diluent. (1000 μ g/ml, 500 μ g/ml). Further 1 ml of above solutions were pipetted into a 10ml standard flask and volume was made up to mark with diluent (CSP: 100 μ g/ml and ETS: 50 μ g/ml)

Optimization of HPLC method

Trials were performed by varying chromatographic conditions like stationary phase, mobile phase composition and buffer pH. Observations were carefully scrutinized for optimizing the method for low retention time, better resolution, theoretical plates and peak symmetry. Some of the trials and their observations are listed in Table 1. The mobile phase and stationary phase were selected based on consideration of the physicochemical properties like log P & pKa and solubility of the two drugs.

Method Validation

Validation of the proposed method was performed following ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines which include system suitability, specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, LOD, LOQ and robustness. Forced degradation studies were performed following ICH Q1A (R2) and Q1B guidelines which include acid hydrolysis, alkali hydrolysis, peroxide degradation, thermal degradation, hydrolytic degradation and photolysis.

System suitability test

A system suitability test was performed to validate measurement system and analytical operations related to the analytical method are suitable for the proposed analysis. Six identical samples were determined.

Specificity

It is the ability to assess the analyte in the presence of expected impurities and degradants by any interference noticed at the retention times of the drugs ETS and CSP. It was determined by comparing the results of blank and placebo solutions.

Linearity

It is the capacity of an analytical method to give test results that are directly proportional to the amount of analyte in the sample within a given range. The linearity was determined by calculating the regression equation from the calibration curve constructed from six standard concentrations.

Precision

Precision denotes the closeness of agreement among a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under set conditions. Precision is considered at two levels: repeatability and intermediate precision. It is expressed in terms of relative standard deviation.

Repeatability: It is the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time. It was assessed by 6 determinations of sample solution.

Intermediate precision: expresses within-laboratories variations: different days, different analysts, different equipment, etc. It is also known as method precision. It was assessed by 6 determinations of 6 different sample solutions on 6 different days.

Accuracy

Accuracy, also known as trueness, expresses the closeness of agreement between the true value and the value found. It is expressed as % recovery, which was determined by spiking known quantities of standards to preanalyzed samples at three different levels.

Limit of detection and limit of quantitation

The limit of detection and limit of quantitation were determined for ETS and CSP at a signal-to-noise ratio of 3:1 and 10:1, respectively, by injecting a series of diluted solutions with known concentrations.

Robustness

It is the reliability of the method concerning deliberate variations in method parameters. It was performed by changing the flow rate and mobile phase.

Forced degradation studies

ICH guidelines recommended stress testing to know the intrinsic stability of drug substances. In these studies, the solution of the standard was subjected to acid degradation (2 N HCl, refluxed at 60 °C for 30 min), alkali degradation (2 N NaOH, refluxed at 60 °C for 30 min), peroxide degradation (20% hydrogen peroxide heated at 60 °C for 30 min), thermal degradation (samples arranged in a hot air oven at 105 °C for 1 h), photolytic degradation (sample in UV chamber for 1 day), hydrolysis (water, refluxed at 60 °C for 1 h). The so-stressed samples were observed for the peak areas and compared with peak areas of the standard.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optimized chromatographic condition:

Various trials were performed by changing the mobile phase and stationary phase using PDA detection at 1.0ml/min flow rate and injection volume 10 μ l. The optimized chromatographic conditions were X-Bridge phenyl, 150x4.6mm, 3.5 as stationary phase coupled with 60volumes Acetonitrile and 40 volumes 0.1% TFA at 1.0 ml/min flow rate with PDA detection, resulted in 2.461min retention time for CPS and 3.893 min retention time for ETS with 6 mins run time at ambient temperature. The optimized chromatogram was presented in Figure 1.

Method Validation

System suitability test

Six identical samples were determined, and the results are shown in Table 2. System suitability test results were within the limit as the % RSD values for retention times, plate count, tailing factor and resolution were less than 2.

Specificity

The proposed method was found to be specific as there were no interfering peaks in the blank, placebo at the retention times of ETS and CSP. The chromatograms of blank, placebo are shown in Figures 2, 3.

Linearity

Linearity of the method was determined by preparing aliquots at 12.50, 25.00, 37.50, 50.00, 62.50, 75.00 μ g/ mL for ETS and 25.00, 50.00, 75.00, 100.00, 125.00, 150 μ g/mL for CSP. The solutions were analyzed in triplicate. The proposed method was found to be linear in the

concentration range of 12.5—75 µg/mL and 25-150 µg/mL for ETS & CSP, respectively. The regression equations for ETS & CSP were found to be $11699x + 3136.4$ for ETS and $16409x + 7883$ Table 3 shows the linearity data of ETS & CSP. The method is said to be linear as the R^2 value of both drugs was found to be more than 0.999. The calibration curves of ETS & CSP are shown in Figures 4 & 5.

Precision

Repeatability and intermediate precision were assessed by 6 determinations of sample solution (CSP (50 µg/mL) and ETS (100 µg/mL)). The results are shown in Table 4. The %RSD values of peak areas for precision were found to be within limits as it is less than 2.

Accuracy

The % recovery was determined by spiking known quantities of standards (ETS and CSP) to pre-analyzed samples at 50%, 100% and 150% levels in triplicate. The results are shown in Tables 5. The mean % recovery was found to be 99.97% for CSP and 100.3% for ETS.

Limit of detection and limit of quantitation

The LOD and LOQ were determined by considering the S/N ratio. The limit of detection values for CSP & ETS were found to be 3 µg/mL and 1.5 µg/ml respectively. The limit of Quantification values for CSP & ETS were found to be 10 µg/mL and 5 µg/mL respectively.

Robustness

It was performed by changing flow rate, 0.9 mL/min (–) and 1.1 mL/min (+) and mobile phase, Buffer: ACN 65:35 (–) and 55:45 (+). The results are shown in Table 6. The % RSD values for peak area were found to be within limits as they were less than 2. So the method was considered to be robust.

Forced degradation studies

These studies were carried out as per ICH Q1A and Q1B guidelines.

Acid degradation 1 mL 2N hydrochloric acid was added to 1 mL standard stock solution of ETS and CSP and refluxed for 30 min at 60 °C.

Alkali degradation 1 mL 2N NaOH was added to 1 mL standard stock solution of ETS and CSP and refluxed for 30 min at 60 °C.

Peroxide degradation 1 mL 20% H₂O₂ was added to 1 mL standard stock solution of ETS and CSP and refluxed for 30 min at 60 °C.

Thermal degradation The standard stock solution was placed in an oven at 105 °C for 1 h to study dry heat degradation.

Photolytic degradation The photochemical stability of the drug was studied by exposing a standard stock solution of ETS and CSP to UV light by keeping the beaker in a UV chamber for one day.

Hydrolysis Stress testing under neutral conditions was studied by refluxing the drug in water for 1 h at 60 °C.

The above solutions were diluted to obtain 100 µg/ mL ETS and 50 µg/mL CSP solutions, and 10 µl of each solution was injected into the system to assess the stability of the sample. The results for ETS and CSP obtained are shown in Table 7. The chromatograms are shown in Figure 6.

CONCLUSION:

The developed method was simple, rapid, sensitive, accurate, precise, linear, specific, robust and reliable. X-Bridge phenyl, 150x4.6mm, 3.5µ as stationary phase coupled with 40 volumes Acetonitrile and 60 volumes 0.1% TFA at 1.0 ml/min flow rate with PDA detection resulted in retention times at 2.461 min for CSP & 3.893 min for ETS. The %RSD of Repeatability of ETS & CSP was found to be 0.51 and 0.47 respectively. The %RSD of intermediate precision of ETS & CSP was found to be 0.48 and 1.11 respectively. Mean % Recovery was obtained as 100.3% and 99.97% for ETS & CSP respectively. LOD and LOQ values obtained from S/N ratios for ETS & CSP were 1.5µg/ml, 5µg/ml and 3 µg/ml, 10µg/ml respectively. The method was found to be linear in the range 12.5-75 µg/ml and 25-150 µg/ml respectively for ETS & CSP respectively with R² more than 0.999. The regression equation for ETS was $y = 11699x + 3136.4$, $y = 16409x + 7883$ for CSP. Stability studies show peak purity in all types of degradation studies for both the drugs. Compared to other methods, the retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased. The proposed method can be used for the quality control of both medicaments simultaneously.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Figure captions

Figure 1: optimized chromatogram of CSP & ETS HPLC method

Figure 2: Blank chromatogram for CSP & ETS HPLC method

Figure 3: Placebo chromatogram for CSP & ETS HPLC method

Figure 4: Calibration curve of CSP

Figure 5: Calibration curve of ETS

Figure 6: Degradation chromatograms for CSP & ETS HPLC method

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Tables:

Table 1: Method development trials for ETS & CSP HPLC method

No.	Column	Mobile Phase	Run time	observation
1.	Symmetry C ₁₈ 150*4.6mm,3.5μ	ACN: H ₂ O 80:20	4min	System suitability not in limit
2.	Symmetry C ₁₈ 150*4.6mm,3.5μ	ACN: H ₂ O 60:40	5min	Unknown peaks are found
3.	Symmetry C ₁₈ 150*4.6mm,3.5μ	ACN: H ₂ O 50:50	7min	Less resolution
4.	Symmetry C ₁₈ 150*4.6mm,3.5μ	ACN:0.1% OPA 50:50	5min	Resolution not within limit
5.	X-Bridge phenyl 150*4.6mm , 3.5μ	ACN:0.1% OPA 50:50	10min	Retention time is very less
6.	X-Bridge phenyl 150*4.6mm , 3.5μ	ACN : 0.1% OPA 30:70	6min	Less resolution
7.	X-Bridge phenyl 150*4.6mm, 3.5μ.	ACN: 0.1% TFA 50:50	8min	Resolution is not good
8.	X-Bridge phenyl 150x4.6mm,3.5μ	ACN:0.1% TFA 60:40	18min	Second peak retention time is very high
9.	X-Bridge phenyl 150*4.6mm, 3.5μ.	ACN: 0.1% TFA 40:60	6min	All parameters within limit. Optimized method

Table 2: System suitability results for CSP & ETS HPLC method

Inj	CSP			ETS			
	Retention time	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	Retention time	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	Resolution
1	2.457	6661	1.02	3.888	8935	1.00	7.75
2	2.456	6689	1.03	3.884	8941	1.02	7.79
3	2.451	6679	1.05	3.883	8964	1.04	7.78
4	2.454	6681	1.06	3.887	8971	1.01	7.80
5	2.459	6680	1.04	3.889	8985	1.00	7.77
6	2.453	6685	1.03	3.882	8980	1.01	7.79
Mean	2.455	6679.2	1.04	3.886	8962.7	1.01	7.78
SD	0.00	9.64	0.01	0.00	20.52	0.02	0.02
% RSD	0.12	0.14	1.42	0.07	0.23	1.49	0.23

Table 3: Linearity data for CSP & ETS HPLC method

Linearity data	ETOPOSIDE		CISPLATIN	
	Inj.	Conc. µg/mL	Area	Conc. µg/mL
1	12.50	147356	25.00	411818
2	25.00	288229	50.00	838822
3	37.50	455265	75.00	1223374
4	50.00	586456	100.00	1645546
5	62.50	737004	125.00	2100828
6	75.00	875525	150.00	2441815
Slope	11699		16409	
Intercept	3136.4		7883	
Correl coeff. (r²)	0.9993		0.999	

Table 4: Precision data for CSP & ETS HPLC method

Peak Area	Repeatability (System Precision)		Intermediate Precision	
	ETP	CPT	ETP	CPT
1	580286	1665540	583125	1650379
2	583277	1652520	584871	1675559
3	580624	1653847	582154	1641358
4	588056	1666328	586245	1654652
5	581947	1663809	581271	1679768
6	585119	1672728	588852	1633883
Mean	583218	1662462	584419.7	1655933
SD	2965.28	7806.24	2825.053	18354.34
% RSD	0.51	0.47	0.48	1.11

Table 5: Accuracy data for CSP & ETS HPLC method

% Level	ETS					CSP				
	API Added (mg)	Actual API (mg)	Amount recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	Level Mean % Recovery	API Added (mg)	Actual API (mg)	Amount recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	Level Mean % Recovery
50 %	25	25.00	25.13	100.5	100.7	50	50.00	49.43	98.9	100.3
	25	25.00	24.98	99.9		50	50.00	50.26	100.5	
	25	25.00	25.4	101.6		50	50.00	50.76	101.5	
100 %	50	50.00	49.87	99.7	100.2	100	100.00	99.34	99.3	100.1
	50	50.00	50.12	100.2		100	100.00	100.29	100.3	
	50	50.00	50.31	100.6		100	100.00	100.62	100.6	
150 %	75	75.00	74.83	99.8	99.9	150	150.00	149.21	99.5	99.5
	75	75.00	75.44	100.6		150	150.00	148.41	98.9	
	75	75.00	74.61	99.5		150	150.00	150.16	100.1	
	Mean % Recovery				100.3	Mean % Recovery				99.97

Table 6: Robustness data for CSP & ETS HPLC method

	ETS				CSP			
	FR (-)	FR (+)	MP(-)	MP (+)	FR (-)	FR (+)	MP(-)	MP (+)
1	779345	295384	654781	424654	2074512	1345612	1844564	1455364
2	776378	292245	651254	422676	2082126	1337434	1863658	1432487
3	777347	294061	656341	423841	2067831	1351159	1852781	1440485
Mean	777690	293897	654125	423724	2074823	1344735	1853668	1445650
SD	1512.95	1575.94	2606.11	994.21	7152.57	6904.4	9577.83	11083.35
% RSD	0.195	0.536	0.398	0.235	0.345	0.513	0.517	0.767

Table 7: Degradation data for CSP & ETS HPLC method

S.NO	Degradation Condition	CSP			ETS			Pass / Fail
		Peak Area	% Recover	% Drug Degradation	Peak Area	% Recover	% Drug Degradation	
1	Acid	1402005	84.4	15.6	495478	85	14.9	Pass
2	Alkali	1419657	85.5	14.5	492514	84.5	15.4	Pass
3	Peroxide	1386314	83.5	16.5	487596	83.7	16.2	Pass
4	Thermal	1601174	96.4	3.6	556532	95.5	4.4	Pass
5	Photolysis	1423065	85.7	14.3	508561	87.3	12.6	Pass
6	Hydrolysis	1594571	96	4	548238	94.1	5.8	Pass

Figures

	Name	Retention Time	Area	% Area	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Cisplatin	2.461	1661674	62.34		1.03	6648
2	Etoposide	3.893	584133	37.66	7.77	1.01	8952

Figure 1: optimized chromatogram of CSP & ETS HPLC method

Figure 2: Blank chromatogram for CSP & ETS HPLC method

Figure 3: Placebo chromatogram for CSP & ETS HPLC method

Figure 4: Calibration curve of CSP

Figure 5: Calibration curve of ETS

Figure 6: degradation chromatograms for CSP & ETS HPLC method